

3.1 Data Sources, Analysis and Emerging Constructs

During the period February 2020 to March 2022, we worked with three local research institutes in the Norwegian node of the eLTER network. We initially used interviews and later observations to understand how data curators work on data on the day-to-day. We also analysed publicly available white papers and documents from eLTER, ESFRI and the Norwegian government to understand the perspective of coordinators of the eLTER open data sharing programme. Taken together, these data collection techniques were useful as they helped us to identify and explore large-scale digitization and data accumulation regulations conveyed by government agencies and funders, and how these are enacted in practice by data curators responsible for the local management of primary data.

Our data sources for this study comprised observation of 19 data curators, including semi-structured interviews with them. Interviews lasted between 45 and 60 minutes, were recorded and thereafter transcribed. In the interviews, we asked questions pertaining to the type and formats of data that data curators worked with, how they collected environmental data, how data were managed including the technologies, sensors, and routines for managing data.

During observations we strived to understand the technologies, materials, data, and data curation models that data curators used in their daily work. We also observed data curators as they conducted field studies, how data was managed for scientific publications, how primary data was managed for public dissemination, individual and collective guidelines for data collection, assurance, quality control, storage, and long-term archiving, how data were shared with partners or outside audiences, where primary data were stored and how they were accessed and other related data management concerns.

Document analysis helped us to understand how large-scale and data accumulation policies and funding initiatives are communicated by governing and funding agencies to understand how these governance frameworks are mirrored at the local level. Our findings reflect participants' understanding and experience of such initiatives. Preparations for eLTER Open Data sharing began in 2020 and implementation is still ongoing. Participant responses are informative because they reveal data curators' understanding of how their current data management practices can provide a needed substrate for the growth and future of eLTER Open Data sharing.

To analyse our data, we followed a stepwise-deductive induction approach (Tjora 2019). We focused our analysis on the data curators and what they did daily in terms of caring for data. We explored their interpretation of eLTER Open Data sharing and their actions in the context of long-term data management. The data were first examined to identify statements or actions that reflected practices about data management and its impact on environmental monitoring work, and the larger eLTER network. We analysed the data by reading and sorting participants' words as 'excerpts from data' into 'categories'. Once all the data had been examined, a cross-group analysis followed, which consisted of comparing the categories we had generated to see if they reflected common themes in extant literature. After this, the data was re-explored and re-coded. This iterative exploration resulted in a set of constructs that we considered core to answering our research questions. Table 1 shows the emerging constructs that underpinned our study.

Constructs	Categories	Excerpts From Data
Characterising Data curators consider the physical properties of data collection technologies and characterise their present and future management needs.	Different methods and routines required for managing different data types	<i>"it is unfeasible to do everything manually, and this is where remote sensing comes into play. We go to selected spots and collect field data at some places. We sometimes use comparison methods to fill the gaps in a more timely fashion in cases where there are missing data"</i> (Data curator 1, interview) <i>"...with fresh water, the sensors that are available there are expensive, and you don't necessarily put out a lot of those"</i> (Data Curator 2, field notes)
	Appropriate documentation of	<i>"as soon as you need an interpretation of what type of plant species has been captured by the sensor, that is</i>

	relevant data interpretations and changes	<p><i>something that requires human interaction. At least for plants when you determine species, you need to have humans that collect the data to interpret the data through appropriate documentation” (Data curator 2, interview).</i></p> <p><i>“Sometimes acoustic devices cannot distinguish the species of bird by their sound. And in an environment where there are different species of bird making similar sounds human interpretation is required” (Data curator 17, interview)</i></p>
	Improving reliability in sensor techniques through ‘on-the-go’ routines	<p><i>“...research areas like wildlife tracking rely on sensors to be effective” (Data curator 5, field notes)</i></p> <p><i>“if none of the data must get lost, then people would use techniques [through which] they can send the data over” (Data curator 14, interview)</i></p>
	Determining specific immediate data use needs vs future data sharing needs	<p><i>“[With] large amounts of data, storage is a challenge. So you have to build good routines to avoid storing data that you don’t need. [...] Some people have routines where they fetch data from specific times they are interested in, process it, and delete it afterward. Then they keep the results to minimize the storage requirements” (Data Curator 3, interview)</i></p> <p><i>“...when you start using sensor-based data, then you need to have the technology to store the data and analyze the data, that can prevent you from sharing all the data” (Data Curator 6, field notes).</i></p>
Augmenting Data curators identify data issues in digital data to complement immediate scientific work and future data release with accurate and interpretable primary data	Conducting science research while cleaning primary data	<p><i>“we have an automated procedure that detects missing values in the database and flag them or notify us. We go into the database and determine why there is a missing value in there and correct them if it is possible” (Data Curator 13, field notes).</i></p> <p><i>“we use the data for our own publications, and we are also doing data wrangling because we have to share the data” (Data Curator 13, field notes)</i></p>
	Data Cleaning involves human agency	<p><i>“sometimes the cameras show certain blurry images that our machine learning program flags as not lynx, but when you review the image, you know that this is a lynx and the program got it wrong.”(Data Curation 12, field notes)</i></p> <p><i>“we use this machine learning algorithm (pointing to her computer screen) which detects the lynx” .”(Data Curation 10, field notes).</i></p> <p><i>“after students have verified output of the machine learning algorithm, we also validate the work of the students, we document all these, and then we communicate it to the data science guys who improve the algorithm” (Data Curator 10, field notes).</i></p>
	Data Description is needed if future users are to understand the context of shared data	<p><i>“We describe the data with metadata. The purpose of metadata is that somebody else should be able to take that data set understand enough about how that data have been collected the kind of sensor used, for instance, if it’s sensor data, the kind of settings used in the sensor, so that they are able to use it again without the special</i></p>

		<i>knowledge of the person who actually collected it.” (Data curator 3, interview).</i>
	Data Wrangling techniques are diverse in practice	<p><i>“...the speed of wind changes continuously so when the same value is recorded repeatedly then we know a problem has occurred” (Data Curator 13, field notes)</i></p> <p><i>“sometimes the depth of the water measurements creates suspicions, maybe the sensors are not submerged deep enough” (Data curator 2, interview).</i></p> <p><i>“sometimes we know that the data should fall within a range for example relative humidity is always between 0% and 100%, any value outside this range shows that there is an error in the data, sometimes also, the bounds are not absolute, so we have to check historical or long-term data that usually show data on extreme values which are useful to set appropriate bounds.” (Data curator, 7, field notes).</i></p>
Liaising Data curators network or liaise with colleagues within the network to align data sharing and science research with the growing data infrastructure	Forming network-level groups	<p><i>“A critical point for the success of the data managers group was the recognition that there were legitimate reasons for some differences between the systems at each site. [...] As far as the group is concerned, you also accept views that are different from your own. There are a variety of approaches between sites, and there is strength in diversity. The goal is to implement and develop the eLTER data infrastructure together.” (Data curator 9, interview).</i></p> <p><i>“You are always connected, affiliated, associated with the community, and that gives the eLTER open data infrastructure that continuity.” (Data Curator 8, interview)</i></p>
	Sharing ideas on cultural differences in terms of science work and data management	<i>“It’s safe to say things that show examples where you have not been as successful, or disappointments even how they plan funding of data management activities. Once you can do that in a group, there is a bond. The group has taken the time to promote an inclusive, sustainable approach to technology and to make sure that we learn together.”(Data curator 10, interview)</i>
	Building a community with continuity	<p><i>“We do not have to rebuild every time, we have built trust. It’s good to see how other sites are doing, either as a contrast or as a suggestion for improvement.” (Data curator 10, interview)</i></p> <p><i>“many of the good ideas that work also come from below, not just from above” (Data Curator 11, interview)</i></p>

Table 1 Emerging Constructs